

SMART AND SECURE IOT-BASED PARKING MANAGEMENT

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Abstract. Vehicles have been one thing that has helped people since it was created. Many have come out and are invented in various forms now and are still being used to make way to get to a destination. However, the vehicle was created not only to be a bridge somewhere but also for drivers who want to feel comfortable, safe, and sound. The vehicle is now one of the biggest helps to people that's why the increase in cars and motorcycles cannot be stopped. But now the vehicle is causing so much traffic because it does not balance the amount of vehicle and parking area, so this is the current problem of the various establishments. Lack of parking lot, lack of security, and lack mainly due to uncontrolled entry causes traffic jams and wrong parking alignment which has been a big problem till now. There is a lot of complication and hard time that does not match, but because of the perseverance of the proponents to make it happen and share it such an invention, is much improved and continues to be possible in this instance. In addition, the overall effort has been made in a way that would be achievable, to be distributed in today's era that seems to have more and more vehicles that require sufficiently fast, smart technology, safe and secured of every driver's vehicle. The implementation of the project would not only reduce the risk of the car and motorcycle being stolen without knowing the driver, but this can also help each of every driver to monitor and sight their vehicle without their presence in the parking area. Not only to help the individual user but also to help the school maintain a good reputation, peace, and security.

Keywords. Parking Management System, Internet of Things, Smart, Secure

1 Introduction

In most countries, vehicles are the dominant mode of transportation, and parking is a feature of every city and suburban area. A parking lot is a space intended to safely store vehicles that would not create any disturbance within the scope of jurisdiction. A parking lot is a designated area for parking. Typically, parking spaces are marked on the ground with white or yellow lines forming squares that fit into a car, frequently straight lines or slants. Parking space is near typical malls, shops, stadiums, bars, restaurants, schools, and other similar spots often featuring ample parking. There are parking lots open over the year for special occasions, but improvised parking lots are made especially for an event. For example, when there is a concert and music festival that occurs only once a year, people may decide to open a nearby meadow to provide parking spaces for the guests of that particular music festival.

Parking space is a significant issue in urban areas, especially in crowded places in developed and developing countries. Many cities are suffering from the lack of vehicle parking spaces with an imbalance between parking supply and demand that can be considered a primary reason for the problems in the metropolis' parking lot. The other visible problem of the proponents is the constant entry of vehicles into a facility. Although there is no space left for the following cars and motorcycles, access to different types of vehicles continues. And it is no longer monitored whether the parking space is enough for that particular vehicle that has already entered. It causes traffic, double parking, complicated parking scenarios, and others crossing the right line, leading to the wrong parking system. Due to the complex parking area and lack of monitoring can also enter crimes such as theft and the owner's vehicle's exploitation. It might be destroyed and stolen since no one sees it, and every time a place is loaded, and you're in line at the main entrance, you are bombarded with the problem of getting out of the queue. Which causes inconvenience to both you and your fellow drivers.

Nowadays parking is becoming a big problem and burden for every facility due to the uncontrollable increase of vehicles. Upon entering a facility, a big test would immediately show up, finding a place to park their cars and motorcycles long inside. These various scenarios consume time and fuel and bring traffic to uncontrollable entry. The parking lot management system's goals include counting the number of parked vehicles, monitoring the parked vehicle's changes over time, and identifying the stalls available (Bibi et al., 2017). In the early times, the concept of intelligent cities gained great popularity. The proposed Smart Parking system consists of an on-site deployment of an IoT module used to monitor and signal the state of availability of a single parking space (Nandyal et al., 2017). Introduces the concept of using IoT-

based technology in car parking systems. Their solution makes the parking system smarter by harnessing IoT-based power and embedding it in the latest innovations in sensors, electronics, and computers (Abdulkader et al., 2018). Using the QR (Quick Response) Code system applying the system with digital features and hoping to help the concept of an intelligent parking system, the driver saves time and creates a well-organized parking system that uses the QR Code for user convenience. QR codes provide a way to share many different information variations with the public effectively. Researchers propose integrating QR code systems and corresponding smartphone applications into existing government services to provide a new level of interactivity capability. The use of a QR (Quick Response) code and a dedicated app can overcome the problems of the existing parking system (Faza et al., 2020).

These are the reasons why the proponents decided to develop this idea due to the researchers' perceived gap for the last innovation. Proponents proposed a project that would make it more useful and a relief to our drivers. At the entrance, the proponents shall add a QR code for the user and visitor to use every time they enter and exit the parking site for security purposes. Monitor the parking area's situation to handle the vehicle volume to enter, and control the dire situation, and scenario for a good parking view. Attach an LED display, buzzer, and surveillance camera in the parking slot for the driver's awareness of the proper alignment position and the user's benefits to sight and monitor their vehicle from time to time using the application. Likewise, we help our drivers from afar to view and watch exactly where the parking slot is available using this application. There, they can avoid the hassle of a place and help their fellow drivers. It is a big deal to solve small things to continue developing an area within its scope.

2 Review of Related Literature

In this modern generation, the number of vehicles is rapidly increasing. A survey revealed that the vehicle population would increase to 1.6 billion around 2035, and nearly a million barrels of oil would burn to perform these vehicles. Every day, in metropolitan cities, the number of cars increases which needs to be maintained by proper management. Drivers generate 30% of traffic in towns (Bulturbayevich et al., 2020). In densely populated areas such as cities, parking spaces are often less than the availability of vehicles, leading to a shortage of parking space. Thirty to fifty percent of drivers are looking for free parking spaces in dense environments worldwide. Based on previous studies, drivers take between 3.5 and 14 minutes to find a parking space. Examples of consequences are driver failure, accidents, loss of business opportunities, congestion, and increasing air pollution. Can observe congestion when traffic density increases, scanned during peak traffic periods (Paidí et al., 2018).

In the works of (Bibi et al., 2017), most parking areas are manually operated by human staff without an automated system to collect the parking area properly. There is an excellent analogy to that when a driver enters any parking lot. The drivers should look for some information board that tells them about the status of the parking lot if it is wholly occupied, partially occupied, or vacant. The drivers need to circle the parking area to look for free parking space most of the time. This type of problem often occurs in cities near shopping malls, hospitals, etc., where the number of vehicles is more significant than parking spaces. The procedure of finding a free parking space is time and fuel-consuming. Most of the time, the parking spaces remained unoccupied with the low occupancy due to inadequate parking lot management caused by inefficient parking areas traffic jams, and congestion near parking lots.

Omar's research found that secure parking in modern cities is a complicated and time-consuming task. Leaving negative implications on traffic congestion may lead to driver's frustration, air pollution, climate change, and others creating challenging situations to find safe parking in the required time. This research aims to design secure and intelligent parking monitoring, controlling, and managing solutions based on the integration. SPS (Smart Parking System) has been suggested and implemented by supporting and resolving this issue. In general, SPS refers to the process of utilizing recent technologies to provide real-time monitoring, controlling, and management for parking lots' status, which may be either vacant or occupied. It can also include many facilities and provide real-time information for discovering parking lots and free space solutions to alleviate traffic congestion, optimize parking management, and improve the user experience while maintaining user privacy and security (Abdulkader et al., 2018).

The researchers explain the architecture and design of responsive authorization using an open-source platform. A basic rule of permission for a user or driver to park a vehicle in the parking place. It a simple yet very effective if the user is authorized personnel and the space is available in the parking lot. The parking gate would open and allow the user to

park the vehicle on the parking premises. An unauthorized user cannot enter a parking area to provide security in a parking site and cars that are already parked (Chaudhary et al., 2017).

Aside from an open-source platform, QR (Quick Response) includes designing and developing the proponent's proposed project. In this regard, Mingliang talked about the topic of QR. There are many kinds of styles of QR codes concerning their design and form. The continued spread of the internet and smart mobile devices has quickly become one of the most widely used information carriers globally. However, the ordinary QR code has a visual-unpleasant display and consists of a monotonic black/white square module with no meaning to the human eye. Therefore, the visual optimization of the QR code has gained wide attraction attention from academia and industry (Xu et al., 2019). QR codes have alphanumeric Max. 4296 characters, some data limits up to Max. 7,089 Numeric characters, and Binary (8 bits) Max. 2953 (Parabhoi et al., 2017).

The researcher also used TCRT5000 as an infrared sensor similar to the Proximity IR sensor used by the proponents. It has both a phototransistor and infrared led integrated into its package. The led has two pins (cathode and anode), which can create an infrared signal. Similarly, the phototransistor also contains two pins (emitter and collector) that can read reflecting infrared signals. It is an ideal sensor for detecting the proximity of an object or any other reflective surface in front of it but is used to see vehicles (Mohammed & Ustun Ercan, 2019).

For the sake of those drivers entering the facility without an application and phone, the proponents continue to make way for the people to make everything quick and advantageous. With the research of mini machine tickets based on IoT, basically from the word itself mini, the thermal printer is small yet can produce quick access for specific uses. Still, as part of the research of the proponents, it concerns the parking lot. A mini machine ticket printer that is small and connected to the database which also programmable to provide a ticket, so the user directly sees the paper mini-making access. Thermal printers work with 5-9 V DC; the greater the voltage applied, the better the result (Lestari & Elvyanti, 2020). In 2018, the researcher started by describing the structure of an intelligent car parking system cloud as a database consisting of three main parts of functionalities: parking part, which includes sensor nodes in indoor car parking, microcontroller devices, and innovative car parking facilities. The second part would be the cloud representing the mediator between the car parking and the user of a mobile phone application. Lastly, the user side is represented by the mobile phone android application. This system has the following functionalities: data processing of sensors locally, the availability of car parking spaces, the ability to guide the user to locate the location of parking spaces and focus on cloud processing rather than network-level processing. Cloud computing is essential for enabling the vision of the IoT from many perspectives, such as data storage and high-power data processing (Alsafery et al., 2018).

3 Project Design and Methodology

Smart and Secure IoT-Based Parking Management minimizes the situation and scenarios inside the parking site. It provides convenience and security for all vehicle owners. This project proposal requires the user's presence to be able to utilize the app and its features. The traditional method of moving into one facility requires a physical scenario to find the right parking slot, which still happens someplace. Through proponents, the proposed project emphasizes the app over the physical situation to prevent and help all the user drivers to perform this project.

This framework shows how the proposed project executes, where an application user connects to a parking site. First, the user must register with integrated CAPTCHA or OTP for human detection to avoid spamming. Login to control and see the app's features and benefits. After the user logs in, the application provides a unique QR code for the passes of the user to enter and exit. This application can be used to monitor the situation inside the parking area; the user can see the place for checking the available space and also a camera in a specific slot for additional benefits of the user to secure and monitor the driver's vehicle through this app even without the presence of the user in parking site. Suppose the vehicle driver is already in that location, a display monitor would show up outside the entrance to check the availability of space inside the facility, and another display monitor at the main entrance before entering. Therefore, everyone who is coming inside that facility would be aware of whether it's already full or not.

The microcontroller with the camera would scan the QR code from the application for the user count and entry. However, assume that the visitor doesn't have an application and phone to enter. Therefore, proponents also provide a thermal printer to the main entrance to give a random printable one-time QR code for visitors for entry and exit use only. The

barrier automatically opens if the QR code is valid and provides a signal to the driver to enter. Imagine an emergency that happened where an original one-time printed QR code went missing, and the security officer has a master key for the emergency exit to at least take immediate action on the visitor's negligence. Suppose the parking slot is limited and some driver is not aware of the alignment inside that parking space, covering the two places that would lead to the wrong parking system, that's why the LED display is in front to show up X mark if it's wrong position and ✓ mark if it's in the correct position and buzzer to remind the driver to park in the right lane.

Figure 1. Operational Framework for the Proposed Project

4 Results and Discussion

Figures 2 and 3 show the proponent's diagram of the possible wiring of microcontrollers and other modules. Existing parking system mechanisms, people tend to say that the simple way to enter is easy to understand and follow. But can easily penetrate their vehicle to bring out without hassle due to lack of security.

The previous parking method was also upgraded with the parking ticket, but still, the same issue, not strictly secured and can still run away the vehicle. Otherwise, proponents improve the way of entering and exiting the parking system by upgrading the LCD a bit larger with a separate microcontroller that covers all the boards connected to the 2 IR sensors after entering and existing for counting. Not only by detecting the vehicle to command the gate to open, but the proponent improves by providing ESP32-CAM as a scanner for the QR code that the user and visitor would be using later on. QR codes for users depending on the mobile, but for the visitor, the proponents also set up a mini thermal printer for random one-time entry QR codes for passes. After scanning the QR code, validation of passes would happen if the passes are valid, the driver would freely enter to park. If not, the gate would not allow anybody to enter. The entirety of the entrance and exit functions and wirings are all connected to a single board.

Figure 4 shows the schematic integrated into the parking layout to understand the position of the modules and identify each part. First, identify the entirety of the project, second is the result of each location of equipment in the miniature parking area, at the entrance proponents provided a sensor to detect the vehicles, LCD for monitoring, ESP32CAM as a scanner, and surveillance camera, servo as gates, thermal printer for visitors to provide QR code, and LEDs to give signals the driver, green for go and red to stop. Third is the parking space itself. There are a lot of sensors to detect vehicles and the alignment, 8x8 LEDMAX, and a buzzer to give awareness to the driver if parked wrong or right.

Figure 2. Schematic Diagram for the Parking Area

Figure 3. Schematic Diagram for the Entrance and Exit

Figure 4. Schematic as Integrated into the Parking Layout

Arduino MEGA and UNO are the heart of the project. It provides enough processing power and memory to run the project, and it can read multiple modules and sensors simultaneously. Eventually, this project needed plenty of Arduino UNO; it was divided into four separate Arduino. The first two would work on parking slots for cars and motorcycles. It contains IR sensors, a buzzer, and an 8x8 LED Matrix Display module. The other one would be the back body of the 3.5 LCD, and the last one is for the main gate containing LEDs, SG90 servo motor, repeatedly with IR sensors, and Mini Thermal Printer. Add on the ESP32-CAM run separately through WIFI that connects to the Arduino board.

Figure 5. ESP32-CAM with Wi-Fi and Bluetooth Module

To add wireless communication between ESP32-CAM and an android phone, a Wi-Fi and Bluetooth module is connected to and pin of the board that would later receive data from the mobile application. This hardware composes plenty of microcontrollers, IR sensors, Buzzers, 8x8 LED matrix displays, 3.5 LCD, LEDs, SG90 servo motors, and a Mini thermal printer used for starters and later on for preparation to the completion of the project.

To create and debug the program to be uploaded in the Arduino microcontroller, the proponents used a programming tool called Arduino IDE. The proponents chose the Arduino IDE because it is the official programming IDE for the Arduino microcontrollers and avoid Hassle adding plugins in other programming software. Before coding the main project, the proponents first test the Arduino board by coding a simple 8x8 LED matrix by programming \checkmark and X mark Figure 6.

Figure 6. 8x8 LED Matrix \checkmark and X Mark

After the various tests of the sensor and servo motor, the proponents can now command how far or how sensitively accurate the IR sensor is by adjusting the back of the module and the right-angle degrees that the servo would turn. However, the proponent adds an LED light to turn green when detecting vehicles entering or exiting, and red would be neutral. Otherwise, the buzzer would be optional, which the proponents just added to the codes but still working. However, proponents were removed due to a lack of wires.

Figure 7. Sensitivity and right degree angle of servo motor

```
when loginbtn Click
do
  call FirebaseDB1 GoValue
  do
    call FirebaseDB1 GoValue
    valueToStore = Username . Text
    valueToStore = Password TextBox2 . Text
    set Label7 Text to Registration Successful
    set Username . Text to
    set Password TextBox . Text to
    set Password TextBox2 . Text to
    set Registration . Visible to false
    set DIP . Visible to true
    set DIP Verified . Visible to false
  if isEmpty Username . Text
  then
    set Label7 Text to Fill out fields
    set registerbtn Enabled to false
  else if not isEmpty Username . Text
  then
    set registerbtn Enabled to true
    set Label7 Text to Registration Successful
  else
    set registerbtn Enabled to true
    set Label7 Text to Registration Successful
  set registerbtn Enabled to true

when registerbtn Click
do
  set Login . Visible to false
  set Home . Visible to false
  set Registration . Visible to true

when FirebaseDB1 GoValue
do
  if get value = Username . Text
  then
    if get value = Password TextBox . Text
    then
      set Login . Visible to false
      set Home . Visible to true
    else
      set Label1 Text to Wrong Username & Password
```

Figure 8. Java Visual blocks

Figure 8 shows the data inserted in FirebaseDB. When the user clicks the login button, it sends the data into FirebaseDB, and the FirebaseDB verifies if the tag is true or equals to the "admin." When the username and password are not equal to the FirebaseDB tag, it would trigger an error that says "Wrong username and password" of the login session. There is also a registration part; when someone presses the register button, it should direct all the information written to the FirebaseDB requested in the register screen. The Username and password would be needed and then will be directly on the OTP screen itself, where the user's email should be asked to validate the entire account.

Figure 9 shows the actual profile screen where the user can edit personal information about the vehicle used. It can add multiple vehicles to one account, and it would update immediately after clicking the button.

Figure 9. Parking Area Monitoring Screen

Figure 10. Parking Area Monitoring Screen

After the proponents divided and assumed the right proportion in the parking area, the proponents were ready to start installing the system inside a miniature parking site. After installing the system, the proponents noticed that too many jumper wires were being used. However, the proponents decided to manage the wires properly to make the work more accessible and less difficult to find wherever it was positioned.

A test run is made before implementing the system in the parking area. Testing is important since this is the best way to ensure the system's integrity. It allows the proponents to identify any errors in the coding and design of the system.

Figure 11. Arduino IDE ESP32 CAM QR

When a user starts scanning the QR code, it would authorize the system and open the gate when the QR code is valid from the mobile application. During this testing phase, the functional test was done. To ensure that the design's coding meets the desired and predicted outcomes, the proponents installed the mobile application on an Android device to this latest version.

A survey is conducted from different types of respondents such as security guards, employees, and visitors with cars and motorcycles results for the effectiveness and security of the project from the users. The proponents prove that the project is successful since respondents answer the survey questionnaires.

Based on the gathered survey for the proposed project, 8 out of 9 questions agreed that the systems' effectivity happens. However, on the other side, 5 out of 5 for the security of the systems properly provided. The overall percentage of "YES" on the question of the system's effectiveness resulted in 88.9%. However, the overall percentage of "NO" on the system's effectiveness has resulted in 11.1%. Since question number 6 hasn't been provided by the proponents, this would hopefully represent passes for visitors without a used mobile phone. Therefore, the proponents did not give the full result of the system.

The overall percentage of "YES" on the question of the system's security has resulted in 100%. The security level was given in full by the proponents. Based on the results of surveys regarding safety, The respondents were happy and satisfied that it has this kind of security that can protect their vehicles even without the driver in the parking area.

The overall project has earned a high percentage of "yes" in the conducted evaluation. All nine questions for the system's effectiveness have an average of 88.9%. In contrast, 11.1% of the evaluators disagreed with one of the questions shown in Table 5, question number 6. Nevertheless, on the other side, for the system's security, the project earned a perfect percentage of "yes" based on conducted evaluation in 5 questions, which is 100% for the level of security.

5 Conclusion and Recommendation

The testing result shows that the proponents can successfully implement the system. The system provided a suitable electronic module to manage and secure the parking area. This system may ease entry and exit by having an active module like servo motors that represent a gate barrier and ESP32-CAM for scanning the codes of every vehicle that enters the school through the help of a QR code that validates every user for security purposes. Proponents assigned an LCD monitoring to find out the specific slot of the newly parked vehicle and the number of available spots. Correct counting and deducting by using IR sensors for the vehicle may help avoid the volume inside; proponents provide everything in one place, especially in parking slots that can give more assurance of every driver inside, a proper parking management system created by the proponents would prevent any damage or obstruction within the parking area by using a sensor to detect exact locations, 8x8 Matrix, and buzzer that reminds the driver to park properly. The level of security perfectly

provided by the proponents 100% answered "YES" in the system's security, the proponents provided not only a QR code pass but also a real-time response of the system. This significant impact, later on, would be a considerable part of camera surveillance that directly focuses on every parking area for cars and motorcycles in the mobile application; and a master key that would be given to the security guards to filter all drivers coming out of school the proponents made this if ever the respondent's loses the QR code passes for security. The system's effectiveness is mostly provided which can be seen in the evaluation result conducted to the end-user with an overall result of 88.9%.

In the future, the proponents should consider adding more big technology to be helpful in today's generation, a design, and suitable enclosure, specifically for all the modules to be preserved further and available for long-term use, especially for a place like a school with many drivers coming in and out a day.

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